

THE PLACE OF UZBEKISTAN'S SCIENCE AND CULTURE DURING WORLD WAR II

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Annotation. *This article is a scientific analysis of data on the history of the contribution of Uzbek scientists to the victory during World War II. It also focuses on the significant impact of research in such fields as geology, chemistry, physics, history, and literary studies on the development of the country not only during the war, but also in the years to come.*

Key words: *Science, defense, tolerance, culture, humanitarianism, geology, history, literary critic, chemistry, physics, archaeologist, lawyer, orientalist.*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqola Ikkinchi jahon urushi yillarida o'zbek ilm-fan namoyondalarining g'alabaga qo'shgan hissasi tarixiga oid ma'lumotlar ilmiy tahlili amalga oshirilgan. Shuningdek, geologiya, kimyo, fizika, tarix, adabiyotshunoslik kabi sohalarda olib borilgan tadqiqotlar nafaqat urush davrida, balki kelgusi yillar davomida ham mamlakatning rivojlanishiga katta ta'sirga e'tibor qaratilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ilm-fan, mudofaa, bag'rikenglik, madaniyat, insonparvarlik, geologiya, tarix, adabiyotshunos, kimyo, fizika, arxeolog, huquqshunos, sharqshunos.*

Аннотация. *Статья представляет собой научный анализ данных по истории вклада узбекских ученых в победу во Второй мировой войне. Кроме того, исследования, проводимые в таких областях, как геология, химия, физика, история и литературоведение, оказали значительное влияние на развитие страны не только во время войны, но и в последующие годы.*

Ключевые слова: *Наука, оборона, толерантность, культура, гуманизм, геология, история, литературовед, химия, физика, археолог, юрист, востоковед.*

It is important to study and correctly understand the history of the activities of the Uzbek people in the fields of science, education and culture during the war years. Uzbekistan not only provided assistance to the front, but also developed socially and culturally, made great efforts to create new knowledge, continue scientific research and educate the younger generation. Changes in the fields of science, education and culture were especially important in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, and in widely promoting humanity and tolerance.

Even today, it is extremely necessary to deeply study this period and preserve its heritage, to convey great historical lessons to the younger generation, and to correctly assess the role and contribution of Uzbekistan in the war in the international arena. In these extremely difficult and dangerous times, the courage and glorious traditions of our heroic veterans will always serve as a school of example for us in fulfilling such extremely important tasks as educating our youth in the spirit of patriotism, protecting our children from various harmful influences, and preserving our invaluable wealth - peace and stability, friendship and harmony between nations and religions[1].

One of the important works carried out in the field of science during the Second World War was the establishment of the "Scientific-Engineering-Technical Society" in Uzbekistan on

November 29, 1941. The purpose of establishing this society was to coordinate the research work of scientists. Uzbek scientists also established close ties with prominent scientists who had emigrated. The research areas of existing and relocated scientific institutions in the republic were revised and adapted to the conditions of the war.

The main attention of scientists was paid to the search for natural resources necessary for the defense industry and their effective use. As a result of the research of geologist H.M. Abdullayev and his colleagues, deposits of tin, tungsten, molybdenum, refractory minerals, rare metals and other raw materials were discovered and developed. A group of geologists led by A. S. Ukionsky discovered an iron deposit, carried out a great deal of work on designing the construction of the Uzbek Metallurgical Combine and putting it into operation. Also, D. M. Bogdanov and engineer G. S. Chikrizov led exploration work in Angren, made a significant contribution to finding rich reserves of coal deposits and building new mines.

Chemists created new effective methods for dewatering oil, cleaning gold from matches, coking coal, using cotton waste in the national economy, and obtaining ethyl alcohol, soda, and acid. Also, as a result of research on the preparation of medicines, various medicines necessary for the needs of the population were developed. A pharmaceutical plant was built and put into operation in Tashkent.

The All-Union Cotton Research Institute conducted fruitful research on the cultivation of new varieties of cotton. Breeders S. S. Kanash and A. I. Avtonomov, under the leadership of whom they created a new variety of cotton resistant to wilt disease. The high-yielding varieties S-460 created by S. S. Kanash and F-108 created by L. V. Rumshevich, as well as other long-fiber varieties, made a great contribution to the development of cotton growing. In 1944, American cotton varieties planted in Uzbekistan were completely replaced by new varieties[6].

Scientists of the republic, in collaboration with employees of the Timiryazev Agricultural Academy in Samarkand, introduced the method of alternating planting of cotton, wheat, and sugar beet. This greatly contributed to obtaining a bountiful harvest of sugar beet in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

During the war years, the humanities also developed significantly. Prominent historians, archaeologists, lawyers, orientalists, and literary scholars, together with their Uzbek colleagues, studied important issues of the history, culture, and literature of the peoples of Uzbekistan. V.S. Struve, V.A. Shishkin, Y.E. Bertels, I.K. Ddonov, V.Y. Zohidov, H.Sh. Inoyatov, A.Y. Yakubovsky, M.Y. Masson, S.P. Tolstov, Y.G. Gulyamov, and others created a number of important works on the ancient and medieval history, material culture, and spirituality of Uzbekistan, as well as the ethnogenesis of the peoples of Central Asia[4].

Also, work began on the two-volume “History of the Peoples of Uzbekistan”. Under the leadership of writer Alexei Tolstoy, Russian and Uzbek scholars jointly created the “History of Uzbek Literature”.

On November 4, 1943, the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan was established, and the famous scientist T. N. Qori Niyozzi was elected its first president. The opening of the Academy of Sciences became an important foundation for the further development of science in the republic. Soon new scientific institutions were established. On the basis of the Institute of Language, Literature and History, the Institutes of History and Archaeology, Language and Literature, Oriental Studies, Economics, Mathematics and Mechanics, Soil Science, Physics and Technology, and other laboratories were established[2:487].

Scientists from the Institute of Oriental Studies have studied manuscripts written in Persian, Arabic and Turkic languages, creating the richest collection of Oriental manuscripts.

This collection consists of 3 volumes, in which about 300 manuscripts are described and scientifically evaluated. The collection is recognized as one of the richest collections of manuscripts in the world.

Postgraduate studies were established in 1944 by the Presidium of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, and 60 people, including 41 Uzbek scientists, were admitted that year. In 1944, 2 doctoral and 17 candidate dissertations were defended at the institutes of the academy. During the war years, Uzbek scientists carried out more than a thousand scientific works, many of which were of great importance for the national economy and defense[3:482].

By 1945, 23 scientific institutions, including 2 scientific research institutes, 2 laboratories and experimental stations, began to operate within the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. The Academy had 3 honorary members, 15 full members, 20 corresponding members and 1265 scientific workers. Among them were 54 doctors of sciences and 172 candidates of sciences. These scientists conducted research in various fields and made a great contribution to the national economy and defense sectors[4]. Also, doctors of physical and mathematical sciences T.A. Sarimsakov and V.I. Romanovsky, geologist H.M. Abdullayev, physicist S.U. Umarov, philosopher I. Muminov, writer S. Ayniy, writer Oybek, poet G. Gulom and others achieved great success in their scientific activities[7].

In conclusion, the rapid development of Uzbek science during the war years made a significant contribution to strengthening the country's economic and defense potential. The establishment of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan and the expansion of its activities made it possible to coordinate scientific research and more effectively apply scientific and technical achievements. As a result of the joint efforts of Uzbek and other Soviet scientists, new scientific institutions, laboratories and research institutes were established, which led to new discoveries and achievements in all areas of science and technology.

Research in such fields as chemistry, physics, geology, history, and literary studies had a great impact on the development of the country not only during the war, but also in the following years. Members of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, including prominent scientists, achieved significant achievements in the fields of reconstruction of the national economy and defense through their scientific work. Developments in the fields of oriental studies and history, as well as in the fields of cotton industry, agrarian economics, and medicine, contributed to the development of all aspects of society.

In general, scientific research and discoveries during the war years strengthened the scientific potential of Uzbekistan, made a significant contribution to ensuring the country's defense and economic security, and this process expanded further in subsequent years, leading to successes in all areas of science and technology.

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